

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF VATAJA ABHISHYANDA (SIMPLE ALLERGIC CONJUNCTIVITIS): A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Abhishyanda* is the prime cause for all the eye diseases and it is also said as *Aupasargika Roga*. Though it has been said that the disease *Abhishyanda* is a curable entity but if not treated properly, it can damage vision and lead to blindness.

Aims and Objective: This study aims to achieve effective treatment of *Vataja Abhishyanda* using Ayurvedic medicines, without causing side effects. **Materials and Methods:** Patient diagnosed with *Vataja Abhishyanda* were selected from the outpatient department of *Shalakyatantra* Jamnagar. The study is a case report done on OPD basis to study the pre and post-effect of the treatment. *Shigru-Haridradi* eye drops 2 drops TDS and 5gm *Haridrakhanda* and *Triphala, Lodhra* for eye wash (*Netra Prakshalana*) twice a day given for next 14 days along with *Erandbhrishta Haritaki* and *Hingwashtaka Churna* for constipation, indigestion and feeling bloating. The

follow up period is of 2 weeks. **Results:** Properly administered Ayurvedic treatments can be highly effective and are generally well-tolerated, making them a preferable choice for those seeking minimal side effects. **Conclusion:** The use of *Shigru-Haridradi* eye drops, *Haridrakhanda* and *Triphala - Lodhra Netra Prakshalana* helps in alleviating the symptoms of patients with *Vataja Abhishyanda* (Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis).

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda, Haridrakhanda, Lodhra, Shigru-Haridradi* eye drop *Triphala Vataja Abhishyanda*.

INTRODUCTION

There are four types of Abhishyanda explained in traditional Ayurvedic literature, with the symptoms of *Vataja Abhishyanda* including *Nistoda*(pricking pain), *Stambhana*(stiffness of the eye), *Sangharsha*(foreign body sensation), *Parushya*(hardness of eyelids), *Ragata* (redness), *Alpa Dushika*(scanty discharge), *Shishirashruta*, *Achchasruta* (clean/watery discharge), *Shankh-Lalat Tod*(pain in temporal and frontal region)*Alpa soph*a(mild inflammation), *Kandu*(itching), *Daha*(burning sensation). So symptoms of the Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis like watery discharge, itching, burning sensation can be considered under the concept of *Vataja Abhishyanda*. Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis is a non-infective type of conjunctivitis in which inflammation of conjunctiva occurs due to allergic or hypersensitive reactions by dust, pollen, air pollution and other environmental factor which may be immediate or delayed.^[1] Hence, the symptoms of Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis, such as watery discharge, itching, and burning sensation, can be interpreted as part of *Vataja Abhishyanda*.

CASE REPORT

A 38-year-old male patient came to our *Shalaky*a *tantra* eye o.p.d. of Institute of teaching and research in ayurveda with the chief complaints of redness, foreign body sensation, and watery discharge and itching in both eyes for the past 4 days. Despite using modern eye drops for the last 3 days, he did not experience any relief. He had similar recurrent episodes since past 3-4 month.

History of Present Complaints: A 38year old male patient came to the eye opd in afebrile and conscious state. He was apparently normal before 4 month ago than he had suffered from redness, foreign body sensation and watery discharge from both eyes. He took allopathic medications for the same. But the recurrence of the complaints has been noticed after that since last 3-4 days, he is having the same complaints. Also, patient had constipation, indigestion and bloating feeling from 20 days. So he came here for Ayurvedic management for his complaints.

Personal and Demographic Data

Age - 38year

Sex- Male

Occupation- Navy officer

Diet -Mixed

Appetite-Moderate

Bowel: Constipated, Irregular

Micturition: 5-6 time per day

Sleep: 7-8 hr. per night, Once a night

Addiction: No addiction

Prakruti: Vata-Pitta.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

SUBJECTIVE CRITERIA

Table no. 1

Redness (<i>Ragata</i>)	Score
No Congestion	0
Mild - occasional congestion with clear pattern of blood vessels	1
Moderate - intermittent congestion with clear pattern of blood vessels	2
Moderate - congestion with the disturbed pattern of blood vessels	3
Clean/Watery discharge (<i>Achhasruta</i>)	Score
Absent	0
Mild and occasionally need to wipe	1
Mild but intermittently need to wipe	2
Moderate and need to wipe frequently	3
Severe and need to wipe almost all the time	4
Foreign body sensation (<i>Sangharsha</i>)	Score
Absent	0
Occasionally present, mild, and not troublesome	1
Intermittently present mild and troublesome	2
Frequently present, moderate, and troublesome	3
Present almost all the time, severe and continuously troublesome	4
Itching (<i>Kandu</i>)	Score
Absent-no itching	0
Occasional tickle sensation not requiring to rub eye	1
Intermittent tickle sensation not requiring to rub eye	2
Continuous itch which requires rubbing of eyes	3
An incapacitating itch which would require significant eye rubbing	4

OBJECTIVE CRITERIA

Table no. 2

Papillae (upper eyelid)	Score
Normal tarsal conjunctiva	0
Multiple small papillae with smooth velvety appearance	1
Micro papillae, each with a diameter of 0.3-1.0mm	2
Giant papillae, each with a diameter of > 1.0	3
Large enormous protruding papilla	4

Papillae (Lower eyelid)	Score
Normal tarsal conjunctiva	0
Multiple small papillae with smooth velvety appearance	1
Micro papillae, each with a diameter of 0.3-1.0mm	2
Giant papillae, each with a diameter of > 1.0	3
Large enormous protruding papilla	4

Congestion (Bulbar conjunctiva)	Score
No Congestion	0
Mild- occasional congestion with clear pattern of blood vessels	1
Moderate - intermittent congestion with clear pattern of blood vessels	2
Moderate - congestion with the disturbed patterned of blood vessels	3
Severe - Velvety conjunctiva with loss of pattern of blood vessels	4

INTERVENTION

After observing all signs and symptoms of *Vataja Abhishyanda* (Simple allergic conjunctivitis) treatments were advised as mentioned below.

Table no.3

No	Drug	Dose	Route of administration	Duration
1	<i>Hingwashtaka churna</i>	5gm with ghrita	Oral	1 week
2	<i>Erandbhrishta Haritaki churna</i>	5gm with lukewarm water	Oral	1 week
3	<i>Shigru Haridradi eye drop</i>	2 drop thrice a day	Local	2 weeks
4	<i>Haridrakhanda</i>	5gm twice a day with lukewarm milk (before meal)	Oral	2 weeks
5	<i>Triphala+Lodhra Churna</i>	3gm Triphala+3gm Lodhra churna	Local	2 weeks

Follow up: 2 weeks after completion of the treatment.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

Table no. 4

BT Torch light examination			Torch light examination AT		
Right eye		Left eye	Right eye		Left eye
Upper swelling	Eyelids	Upper swelling	Normal	Eyelids	Normal
Severe Congestion on upper and lower	Palpebral conjunctiva	Severe Congestion on upper and lower	Normal	Palpebral conjunctiva	Normal
Moderate congestion	Bulbar conjunctiva	Severe Congestion	Normal	Bulbar conjunctiva	Normal

Normal	Cornea	Normal	Normal	Cornea	Normal
NSNR	Pupil	NSNR	NSNR	Pupil	NSNR
Normal	lens	Normal	Normal	lens	Normal

Visual Acuity

Table no.5

BT				AT		
VA	DVA	Pin Hole	NVA	DVA	Pin Hole	NVA
RE	6/6	6/6	N/6	6/6	6/6	N/6
LE	6/6	6/6	N/6	6/6	6/6	N/6

Slit Lamp Examination

Table no.6

	BT	AT
Right eye	Papillary changes on whole UPC and LPC Congestion present on bulbar conjunctiva. Watery discharge present +	No any papillary changes and Congestion marked on conjunctiva
Left eye	Papillary changes on whole UPC and LPC and Watery discharge present + 1 small concretion present on LPC	normal UPC and LPC mild congestion present on bulbar conjunctiva

Changes observed in subjective criteria after treatment

Table no. 7

subjective criteria	BT		AT	
	Right eye	Left eye	Right eye	Left eye
Redness	2	2	0	0
Clean watery discharge	3	3	0	0
Foreign body sensation	2	2	0	0
Itching	2	2	0	0

Changes observed in objective criteria after treatment

Table no. 8

objective criteria	BT		AT	
	Right eye	Left eye	Right eye	Left eye
Papillae (Upper eyelid)	2	2	0	1
Papillae (Lower eyelid)	2	1	0	0
Congestion (Bulbar conjunctiva)	3	2	0	1

DISCUSSION

Before *Koshtha Shodhna Deepana Pachana* was done with *Hingwashtaka Churna*.^[2] It has *Shunthi* due to its *Katu Rasa* and *Ushna Veerya* property increases the *Agni* (digestive fire).

There by relieves *Mandagni* and indigestion. Other contents of *Hingwashtaka Churna* also help in *Vata-Anulomana* and *Deepana Pachana Karma*.

Erandbhrishtha Haritaki was given for *Koshtha Shodhan* which contains *Erand Taila* and *Haritaki*.^[3] *Haritaki* is *Deepana, Pachana, Srotoshodhaka*, due to *Ushna Virya* and *Laghu Guna*, performs the *Anulomana Karma* due to *Amla Rasa, Madhura Vipaka*. *Erand Taila* has ability to digest *Sama Dosha* and expels in the *Nirama* form.

Triphala-Lodhra Kashaya was given to the patient for *Netraprakshalana*. *Triphala* contains *Amalaki, Haritaki, Vibhitaki* which possess mainly *Ruksha* and *Ushna* and *Tridoshara* properties and *Lodhra* has *Kaphapitta Shamaka* properties. Which has played a supportive role in alleviating the patient's symptoms.

In this case study we used *Shigru-Haridradi* eye drop which is in form of *Aschyotana* and prepared by the distillation process.^[4] *Shigru-Haridradi* eye drops contains *Shigru, Haridra, Daruharidra, Yashtimadhu* and *Madhu* (Honey) which having *Vata-Kapha Shamak, Shothahara, Vedana Sthapaka* properties Which alleviated the foreign body sensation and reduced the watery discharge.

Oral drug *Haridrakhanda* is selected for this case study which is *Kandughna* property indicated in *Sheetapitta* (Urticaria) by *Bhaisajya Ratnavali*.^[5] In *Haridrakhanda, Haridra* have *Shothahara, Kandughna, Vishaghna, Raktashodhaka Karma* and anti-allergic property.^[6] Other ingredients like *Triphala, Trivrita, Trikatu, Vidanga, Musta* and *Chaturjata* act as a *Kandughna* and *Vata-Kapha Samaka*.^[7] Most of the ingredients having properties like *Deepana, Amapachana, Anulomana*. So, *Haridrakhanda* was selected for this study

Both drug act as *Vata-Kapha Samaka, Shothahara, Kandughna* leading to reduced itching, redness, foreign body sensation, and watery discharge. Improvement in these symptoms can cause relief in *Vataja Abhishyanda* (Simple Allergic Conjunctivitis).

After administering 14 days of *Shigru-Haridradi* eye drops, 2 drops thrice daily, *Haridrakhanda* 5gm bd before meal with luke warm milk along with *Netraprakshalana* with *Triphala-Lodhra Kashaya*, most of their symptoms like redness, watery discharge, and foreign body sensation gradually reduced. Along with this, the patient took *Erandbhrishtha Haritaki* at night for 7 days, which resolved his complaint of constipation. Additionally, *Hingwastaka Churna* enhanced the patient's digestive fire (*Agni*) and helped in digestion and

metabolism (*Deepana and Pachana*).

When the patients came for their first follow-up after 14 days, most of their symptoms of *Vataja Abhishyanda* (simple allergic conjunctivitis) had resolved. By the time of their second follow-up, none of the earlier symptoms were observed.

CONCLUSION

The potentiality of Ayurvedic management in treating *Vataja Abhishyanda* (simple allergic conjunctivitis) has been highlighted in this case as a safe and effective alternative to conventional therapy. While further clinical studies are needed, the results suggest a promising role for *Ayurveda* in managing allergic eye conditions.

SOURCE OF SUPPORT

Institute for Post Graduate Teaching and Research in Ayurveda, Gujarat Ayurved University, Jamnagar- 361008, Gujarat india.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: None declared.

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